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Unexplored Built Heritage: Traditional Weaving Community, Varanasi

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Abstract

Built heritage is considered as one of the supreme valuable cultural gifts to any region. It depicts layers of our historical built heritage which is made up of mud, brick, stone, bamboo and thatch. It includes house, markets, clubs, museum, industry and so on. The importance of built heritage and possibly more significant how that significance to be explain. Different aspects of heritage have been reviewed in the past to understand the possibility of different questions that may bearish in the future regarding its preservation. With the key objective to identify and analyse which dimension of built heritage of handloom weavers of Varanasi to be called as unique and why, What are the different aspects that makes it distinctive from other professions in Varanasi the topic has been taken. Several research are going on to understand the challenges faced by the community to preserve their unique and valuable built heritage. Primary survey and secondary data have been used for the collection of valuable information about the study area. The Qualitative and quantitative approach has been used for the insight analysis to get the desired result.

Based on empirical knowledge and global experience in terms of built heritage of handloom weaving and understand local perception about built heritage, a household survey has been conducted in Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, in June 2017. Weaver's perception regarding the conservation of their built heritage was very different from the government point of conservation like weavers wants improvement and up gradation in the weaving locality while the government wants to shift their locality to the newer areas where there is better availability of various infrastructure in the form of road connectivity, regular supply of electricity, good availability of drinking water etc.

I have prepared a map of Uttar Pradesh, in the same map Varanasi district is also highlighted by the use of MapInfo software. Primary survey has been tabulated with the help of different techniques. After the discussion, it was also noted that neither the Muslim weaver set their handloom in the west direction where Makkah is located (holiest place of Muslim) nor the Hindu weaver set it according to the Vastu Shastra. Both set their handlooms as per the availability of the space that they have in their handloom room and maximum passage of sunlight in that direction.

Keywords : 1.Built Heritage, 2.Dimension, 3.Challenges, 4.MapInfo and 5.Makkah.

Introduction

Built heritage comprises of all arrangement of human past environment i.e. from ancient assets to the post-war sites including battlefield, painting, pleasure ground and house (Creigh-Tyte, 2000). Such buildings portray significant value to its architect, either in the form of services it delivers, or the monetary prospect it provides (Earl, 2003). Nowadays, modern thought identifies that there are many cases in which the framework of past assets can be assumed. When describing it as a vital part of the larger section of the society (Smith, 2010). A unique creativity of human being; a significant link to human values over the long period of time or within the cultural arena of the globe, valuable development in the art, architecture, archaeological sculpture and urban planning (School of Planning and Architecture, 2015). There is a unique functional classification of work in the weaver's house. Ground floor of weaver's house is used for performing several activities like they have their handloom in one side of the room, in the same room they kept their music system (Fig. 1) to refresh up their mind during long hours of weaving work. On the other side, they kept their

bed to take some sorts of rest when they feel they are tired after longer work of weaving. From other room on the same floor, they sell basic food items to the nearby children to earn some money, in the same room they also make a small storeroom (Fig. 2) for their weaving materials and shop items (One of the respondent, 2017). On first floor, they have small poultry farm with maximum 8-10 cocks and hens. Weavers made a cage for them and that cage is composed of thin iron wire. However, there are several activities like teaching, knitting woollen clothes, rearing of pigeon, preparation of natural lamp etc. are also performed on different floors and in the surrounding of weavers (One of the respondents, 2017).

Historical Background

Initially, Varanasi weavers were engaged in the preparation of cotton sarees. But, in the early seventeenth century with the coming of traders from Murshidabad (today in West Bengal), silk was introduced in Varanasi (Malley, 1997). These traders were very fond of silk products like the royal garment, blanket, curtains etc. To satisfy the demand of traders, Varanasi weavers start preparing silk sarees instead of cotton one. Apart from this, several other reasons are also responsible for the shift from cotton to silk saree (Fig. 3). Cotton weaving is very tough and complicated than the silk saree weaving (Lari, 2010). Per silk saree profit margin was much higher than the cotton one and silk sarees are more eye-catching, gorgeous and nice looking than the cotton one. Cotton sarees are generally used to satisfy the daily uses that's why the consumers of that saree do not want to pay more money for it. On the other hand, silk sarees are wearing in several auspicious occasions like marriage, fairs, festivals etc. and its consumers very happily spend more money to buy to it. With this trend silk sarees gain edge over the cotton saree. Following this, Varanasi cotton saree industry became less popular and many of them were closed. In this way, Varanasi lost its rich cultural heritage of cotton saree (Dhamija, 1970).

Study Area

Varanasi is situated on the banks of sacred river Ganga. It has world famous and holy Buddhist site viz. Sarnath. It is also known for its living tradition, culture and tradition centres like Sarnath as Gautam Buddha cultural centre (State Department of Tourism, 2015). It has total 35 wetlands which is spread over 508130 hectare (Ministry of Environment Forest and Climate Change, 2015). Varanasi is the hub of both tangible and intangible cultural heritage, also known as sacred living city all over the world (Map 1). Few important heritage of Varanasi are as follows 84 ghats, Sarnath, Durga Kund and Sankat Mochan (Indian National Trust for Art and Cultural Heritage, 2015). Varanasi traditionally known as Shiv ki nagri or Banaras and it is wrongly pronounced as Benares, it has record of constant settlement in the human history even before 1000 BCE (Singh, 1993). Varanasi main city mostly grew in the 18th century and in 1991, it has got the tag of million plus city with the total population of 1.4 million which is spread over an area of 85.43 sq. km. (Census of India, 2011). Varanasi comprises of 63% Hindus, 32% Muslims and 5% contributes other population (Statistical Abstract Uttar Pradesh, 2010). Varanasi has been renowned as the centre of civilization, tradition, enlightenment, custom, culture and learning for more than 5000 years. It is situated on one of the world famous trade route and it is also cited by Xuanzang, who was a famous Chinese traveller. For a very short period; it was named as Mohammadabad by Aurangzeb, the Mughal ruler. Aurangzeb, the Mughal ruler.

Map 1 Author, 2016

The city is recognised as holy by Muslims, Buddhist, Jains and Hindus. It is one of the ancient consistent inhabited cities of the world. For Hindus, it is the most sacred place on the earth (Heritage City Development and Argumentation Yojana, 2016).

Objective

1. Which dimension of built heritage to be called as unique and why.

Methodology and Database

Methodology is a path, a path from unknown to the known. It is truly a journey of discovery (Bailey, 1978). My study is based on Primary survey and secondary data. Both qualitative and quantitative approaches have been used. Qualitative approach deals with subjective aspects like human behaviour, thinking, tactic, approach etc. which give us the insight as well as the long-lasting view of respondents and research area. It is used for insight interview and focus group discussion. Quantitative approach concerned with the data generation in a quantitative way. This approach studied the sample of the population to get the desired outcome.

- **Primary Survey** Concerning this purposely random survey was conducted in Varanasi, June 2017. This survey composed of fifty participants, for this I have divided my respondent into different two categories first, who are engage in the core weaving work and second, who are not engage in weaving directly. I have selected twenty-five respondent from each category irrespective of children, female, young, middle and old age. This classification has been done for the inclusive understanding of weaving built heritage. I did a pilot survey of my study area to understand its present and future circumstances. Uttar Pradesh map has been prepared with the help of MapInfo software. In the same map along with all 75 districts, Varanasi is also digitized. Varanasi district is filled with blue colour while rest 74 districts are filled with green colour to differentiate it from the study area i.e. Varanasi to the others. Both close and open-ended questions are prepared for the focus group discussion and insight impression of the built heritage. Different statistical techniques have been used to prepare pie and bar diagram. I have selected this topic because I have a keen interest in the built heritage of weaving community. I have the deeper knowledge of built heritage and can do critical analysis as well. I am also associated with it for a long time and can do insight and deeper analysis rather than choosing a new area of which I don't have a better understanding.
- **Secondary Data** Different sources of secondary data have also been referred. Some of them are as follows. State Department of Tourism Government of Uttar Pradesh, Ministry of Environment Forest and Climate Change, School of Planning and Architecture, Indian National Trust for Art and Cultural Heritage, Statistical Abstract Uttar Pradesh, Census of India, National Handloom Development Corporation, Ministry of Textiles and Heritage City Development and Argumentation Yojana are the rich sources. Along with this, numerous literary works like journals (national and international), magazines, articles, books, gazette, eminent newspapers, headlines and various other key materials from the internet have been used for insight study.

Key Findings

On the ground floor, weavers set their music system to refresh up their mind during weaving. In the profession of weaving, weavers from the different age- groups are involved in it from generations. Weavers above the age of 50 years have the maximum percentage and minimum from the age-group below 25 years (Fig. 7). This is because weavers whose age is above 50 years they can't shift to other professions at this stage of their life while weavers below 25 years are searching other opportunities like teaching, preparing for different government jobs and think weaving as not a good career option. In the same room, they have their

temporary bed for a power nap and are not full bedding (Fig. 4). It is mostly used when weavers feel very tired after the long hour of weaving. Though they have a full bed on the first floor but they mostly avoid to going there because when they go to the first floor then that power nap of half an hour, automatically convert into two to three hours sleep. If this not happens, then they will engage in some other work of their family both will affect their weaving work as well. They take power nap on the available bedding materials like a cot or the folding. On the same floor, they also have a small shop to sell basic items like egg, biscuit, toffee, churan, tea samosa, and local chips. This shop is situated in that room which faces the street when they open the door and window and children are the main consumer of it.

Fig. 1 Music System (Author, 2017)

Fig. 2 Storeroom (Author, 2017)

Fig. 3 Silk Saree (Author, 2017)

Fig. 4 Bedding (Author, 2017)

Fig. 5 Nari with Silver Jari (Author, 2017)

Fig. 6 Young Weaver (Author, 2017)

Percentage of Weavers in Varanasi

■ Below 25 Years ■ 25-45 Years ■ Above 50 Years

Raw Materials Used in Sarees

Raw Materials

On the ground floor, Hindu weavers also do animal rearing. They domesticate mulching animals like buffalo or cow. They prepare a shelter for their animals. Some have a separate room for them and some kept their animals in their courtyard. They mostly sell animal milk and on some occasion, they also consume it themselves. They daily take two tanks filled with milk and deliver it to their nearby customers. They set monthly payment for the delivery of milk and in some household per day payment is also set. On the first floor, Female member (Hindu weaver) of the family give tuition to the child of their locality, these children come from the lower strata of the society. They taught up to class 10th standard in all subjects, for that very basic fee from these children are charged. The timing for teaching starts only after 2pm to 6pm. On the same floor, weavers (female) also wrap different raw materials silver jari, copper jari, cotton and resham (Fig. 8) on Nari, which is locally called as Babin (Fig. 5). All these materials are very costly, handle with very care by the weavers and are kept beyond the reach of children. There is a clear cut division of different work in the weaver's family. Those members, who are engaged in the weaving work of Banarasi saree, do not handle shop, teaching, animal rearing etc. However, they help in the task of one another, when they need help. This reveals the richness of the weaving community built heritage.

Conclusion

With the change in time, taste, profession, need and culture, there is also change in the function of different actions performed by weaver's community like when their grandfather was doing the weaving, and then they have more open and vacant space on different floors of the house. Today, that space has squeezed, because in the same room whole family is living. Sometimes, it became very difficult to wrap and unwrap the yarn from the big cone. Many of the weavers have sold their animals, when they are offered good money for them. Young weavers (Fig.6) do not have the inclination to their ancestral work of weaving because they want to study and interested in the government job, which is permanent and formal. The work of weaving is informal, more and more attention from the government is required to develop the interest of young minds in it with the new and innovative ideas, techniques. Otherwise, this built heritage of weaving community will completely vanish from Varanasi.

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